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Life Satisfaction in the Italian Regions

Between 2010 and 2022 it grew by an average of 5.05%.

Istat calculates the value of life satisfaction in the Italian regions. The variable is represented by the percentage of people aged 14 and over who expressed a life satisfaction score between 8 and 10 out of the total number of people aged 14 and over.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of life satisfaction in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for the value of life satisfaction in 2022 with an amount of 61.8 units. Followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 52.6 units, and Sardinia with an amount of 50.8 units. In the middle of the table are Molise with an amount of 46.9 units, followed by Calabria with a value of 46.8 units, and Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 46.5 units. Puglia closes the rankings with 42.6, followed by Abruzzo with an amount of 41.8 units and Campania with a value of 35.7 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in satisfaction with one's life between 2010 and 2022. Lazio is in first place for the value of the percentage change in satisfaction with one's life between 2010 and 2022 with a value equal to 24.39% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 36.90 units up to a value of 45.90 units. Sardinia follows with a variation of 17.59% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 43.20 units up to a value of 50.80 units. In third place is Umbria with a value equal to +14.45% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 43.60 units up to a value of 49.90 units. In the middle of the table there is Piedmont with a value equal to +6.56% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 45.70 units up to a value of 48.70 units. Basilicata follows with a variation equal to +4.44% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 42.80 units up to a value of 44.70 units. Emilia Romagna follows with a value equal to +3.62% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 47.00 units up to a value of 48.70 units. In the last places Tuscany with a variation equal to -0.67% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 44.50 units up to a value of 44.20 units. Trentino Alto Adige follows with -1.75% and Valle d'Aosta with a value of -5.90%. Considering the average value of satisfaction with one's life in the Italian regions we can see that this value grew by 5.05% between 2010 and 2022.

Satisfaction with one's life in the Italian macro-regions. Satisfaction with one's life grew in the Italian macro-regions with a value equal to +2.71% in the North, equal to 3.13% in the North-West, equal to +1.66% in the North-East, equal to 12.62% in the Centre, equal to 9.00% in the South, equal to 8.00% in the South and 11.48% in the Islands. We can see that life satisfaction has grown more in the central-southern regions than in the central-northern regions.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The following clusters are identified:

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- Cluster 1: Trentino Alto Adige, Valle d'Aosta;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Campania, Puglia, Lazio, Basilicata;
- Cluster 3: Emilia Romagna, Veneto, Piedmont, Marche, Lombardy, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Abruzzo, Sardinia, Liguria, Umbria, Tuscany, Calabria, Molise.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters we can see the following structure: C1>C3>C2. The first cluster, namely C1, is made up of only two regions in the North. In second place are the regions of Cluster 3 which brings together regions of Central, Southern Italy and Northern Italy. And finally cluster 2 made up of some southern regions and Lazio. From this analysis it therefore appears that satisfaction with one's life tends to be higher in the Central-Northern regions compared to the southern regions.

Conclusion. The value of satisfaction with life grew in all Italian macro-regions between 2010 and 2022. However, there are some regions in which the value of satisfaction with life has decreased, for example: Liguria with -0.43% , Friuli Venezia Giulia with -0.64%, Tuscany with -0.67%, Trentino Alto Adige with -1.75%, Valle d'Aosta with -5.90%. That is, satisfaction with one's life has decreased especially in the Central-Northern regions. However, Southern Italy is the part of the country that has the lowest level of satisfaction with one's life. In fact, the level of satisfaction with life in the South is 18% lower than in the North, North-West and North-East, 11.00% lower than the Center and 4.5% lower than the South. However, there is a distinction within Southern Italy and the Islands. In fact, while the value of satisfaction with one's life in the South is equal to 40.5, the same value for the Islands is equal to 46.6. Therefore, the population residing in the Islands appears to be much more satisfied with their lives compared to the other regions of Southern Italy. The value of satisfaction with one's life in the Islands is also higher than in the macro-region of Central Italy. Therefore, we can note that the value of life satisfaction tends to grow with per capita income with the sole exception of the Islands. These data are also in contrast with a vision of Southern Italy as a place where people live well and there is balance in life. In Southern Italy only 40% of the population declares to be satisfied with their life compared to 49.4% in the North West. If we consider the average of life satisfaction in 2022 we notice a value of 47%, which is lower than half of the population. It therefore follows that the majority of the population tends to be dissatisfied with the condition of their lives. The only regions in which more than half of the population declares to be satisfied are Trentino Alto Adige, Valle d'Aosta, Sardinia and Lombardy. It follows that the Italian economy appears to be very weak both in terms of GDP and in terms of the well-being perceived by the population.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

- Piemonte
 ■ Valle d'Aosta
 ■ Liguria
 ■ Lombardia
 ■ Trentino-Alto Adige
 ■ Veneto
 ■ Friuli-Venezia Giulia
 ■ Emilia-Romagna
- Toscana
 ■ Umbria
 ■ Marche
 ■ Lazio
 ■ Abruzzo
 ■ Molise
 ■ Campania
 ■ Puglia
 ■ Basilicata
 ■ Calabria
 ■ Sicilia
- Sardegna

Regione	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	45,7	48,5	41,1	36,2	40,2	38,9	44,6	42,9	43,9	48,7	44	45,6	48,7
Valle d'Aosta	55,9	53,5	43,7	47,1	46,3	48,1	45,8	47,2	51,6	54,7	54	51,7	52,6
Liguria	46,3	53,1	35,5	37,6	39,3	34,8	39,2	41,3	44,8	42,7	46,2	46	46,1
Lombardia	49,1	48,1	40,9	40,7	41,3	40,2	46,8	46,2	47,7	47,4	48,8	48,5	50,1
Trentino-Alto Adige	62,9	60,5	53,9	54	54,2	58,9	59,8	62,3	61,4	62,2	61,8	60,8	61,8
Veneto	46,8	46,4	40,2	40,7	39,7	40,8	44,6	43,3	47,5	43,6	48,4	48,5	47,5
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	46,8	48,8	41,2	42,2	42,8	44,3	45,4	43,4	44,9	46,5	49,4	49,2	46,5
Emilia-Romagna	47	48,8	39	35,6	40,4	38,9	44,6	44	46	44,1	48,2	47,7	48,7
Toscana	44,5	45,7	32,3	35,6	34,6	35,6	43,5	42,3	42,1	42,6	43,6	47,2	44,2
Umbria	43,6	45,4	36,5	36,3	38,5	36,6	41,2	37,2	41,8	47,4	44,6	43,4	49,9

Marche	40,8	47,1	37,8	38,2	35,8	37,9	43,2	40,3	44,2	43,2	47,2	44,4	44,4
Lazio	36,9	39,3	30,9	31,6	34,8	33	37,5	36,9	35,6	41,1	40,7	45,5	45,9
Abruzzo	41,1	46,3	39	37,5	35,4	36,1	43,9	40,7	42,3	47,1	43	45,9	41,8
Molise	46,2	47,5	37,2	35,4	34,8	25,8	37,9	36	36,9	43	44	45,5	46,9
Campania	32,1	38,5	21,8	24,2	20,6	20	28,1	24,9	26,7	31,6	31,7	40,6	35,7
Puglia	39,5	43,8	32,2	29,3	30,3	31,2	38,1	36,3	36,2	41,2	42,8	39,5	42,6
Basilicata	42,8	49,2	30,7	33,2	27,8	25,9	34,5	36,7	44,1	40,3	45,6	42,4	44,7
Calabria	43,1	47,9	33,1	35,4	33,6	32	38,5	34,6	37,9	39,5	47,2	49,6	46,8
Sicilia	41,3	45,7	29	28,2	27,2	29,3	35,3	31,9	37,4	41,9	39,8	43,2	45,2
Sardegna	43,2	45,4	37,9	36,9	35,4	34,9	39,8	41,4	41,7	44,4	46,4	48,7	50,8
	44,8	47,5	36,7	36,8	36,7	36,2	41,6	40,5	42,7	44,7	45,9	46,7	47

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	48	48,8	40,7	39,6	41,1	40,5	45,7	45	47	46,7	48,3	48,3	49,3
Nord-ovest	47,9	48,8	40,5	39,2	40,8	39,3	45,5	44,8	46,4	47,3	47,3	47,5	49,4
Nord-est	48,3	48,8	41	40,1	41,6	42	46	45,3	47,9	45,7	49,6	49,4	49,1
Centro	40,4	42,9	32,7	34,1	35,1	34,7	40,4	39	39,2	42,3	42,7	45,8	45,5
Mezzogiorno	38,9	43,7	29,6	29,6	27,9	28,1	35,1	32,6	35,1	39,2	39,8	43	42,4
Sud	37,5	42,8	28,8	29,2	27,3	26,8	34,4	31,8	33,4	37,6	39	42,2	40,5
Isole	41,8	45,7	31,2	30,4	29,3	30,7	36,5	34,3	38,5	42,5	41,5	44,6	46,6
Italia	43,4	45,9	35,3	35	35,4	35,1	41	39,6	41,4	43,2	44,3	46	46,2

Rank	Regione	2022
	Trentino-Alto	
1	Adige	61,8
2	Valle d'Aosta	52,6
3	Sardegna	50,8
4	Lombardia	50,1
5	Umbria	49,9
6	Piemonte	48,7
7	Emilia-Romagna	48,7
8	Veneto	47,5
9	Molise	46,9
10	Calabria	46,8
	Friuli-Venezia	
11	Giulia	46,5
12	Liguria	46,1
13	Lazio	45,9
14	Sicilia	45,2
15	Basilicata	44,7
16	Marche	44,4
17	Toscana	44,2
18	Puglia	42,6

19	Abruzzo	41,8
20	Campania	35,7

